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Green Infrastructure and Nature Based Solutions Seminar

Program & registrant list

24 February 2020

Event details

Event summary	
Date	Monday 24 February 2020
Time	9.30–2.30pm (including networking lunch from 1.30pm)
Venue	RMIT Europe Media-TIC Building Roc Boronat 117, Level 5 Barcelona 08018
Topic Seminar	<p>Half day seminar and networking event addressing nature-based solutions for sustainable cities.</p> <p>The seminar will bring together leading academics, designers, policymakers, industry leaders and practitioners to explore and discuss Nature Based Solutions (NBS) to address urban societal and environmental challenges.</p> <p>The first half of the seminar will feature presentations and a panel discussion. The second half will include NBS case study presentations from local and international projects. An open dialogue will follow.</p> <p>This seminar is part of the international symposium (<i>Re) Connecting Urban Natures: An interdisciplinary symposium on transforming human-nature relations in cities.</i></p>

Speakers

Marta Fernández
Executive Director, RMIT Europe

In addition to leading the team at RMIT Europe, Marta works with industry in Europe to foster collaborative research and development projects and secure talent for partners. Her areas of expertise are in urban wellbeing and active ageing.

Susana Saiz
Environmental and Sustainability Advisory - Associate Director, ARUP

Sustainability specialist and advocate at Arup with wide experience in sustainable strategy and design, health and wellbeing consultancy. Susana holds a PhD in urban microclimate design influenced by green infrastructures.

Martí Franch
Founder Manager, EMF Landscape Architects

Landscape Architect and Doctor of Design Honoris Causa by the University of Greenwich and Engineer in Agricultural Sciences by ETSAB in Barcelona. Martí is the founder & principal of EMF landscape architects, an interdisciplinary practice of experts in the field of urban and environmental design. Martí is a lecturer at ETSAB in Barcelona and has been a visiting lecturer at different international universities including RMIT.

Speakers

Margarita Parés
Head of Biodiversity, Barcelona City Council

Biologist and specialist in urban ecology and the environment, Margarita has worked for the Barcelona City Council since 1986, and is currently responsible for the Biodiversity Plan of the city. She is co-author of a number of books on biodiversity for the urban environment.

Núria Noguera
Urban Planning Director, OUA Group

Architect and Professor of Urbanism at La Salle University, Núria is the Director of Urbanism at OUA Group. OUA Group is a hub of urban planning, architecture and asset management focussed on problem solving with a multidisciplinary approach.

Event program

Time	Item	Speaker
09.30am	Registration and coffee	
10.00am	Welcome and introduction	Marta Fernández, Executive Director, RMIT Europe
10.15am	1. Measuring the impact of natural capital	Susana Saiz, ARUP
	2. Designing with nature	Martí Franch, EMF Landscape Architects
	3. Green Infrastructure and Nature Based Solutions at the local level: Barcelona	Margarita Parés, Barcelona City Council
	4. Nature at Urban Scale	Núria Noguer, OUA Group
11.00am	Panel discussion	Chair: Marta Fernández Margarita Parés Susana Saiz Martí Franch Núria Noguer
11.45am	Short break	

Event program

Time	Item	Speaker
12:00pm	Nature Based Solutions Case Study Presentations	
	Introduction	Ferne Edwards, RMIT Europe
	1. Urban GreenUP	Cristina Yacoub, Leitat
	2. Huertos in the sky	Adela Martínez, Huertos in the Sky
	3. Anella Verda	Carles Caballero, Terrasa City Council
	4. Hybridising built environment and living systems	Chiara Farinea, IAAC
	5. Espigoladors	Ana Cornudella, Espigoladors
	6. Naturvation	Filka Sekulova, ICTA, UAB
7. EdiCitNet	Cristina González, Sant Feliu de Llobregat City Council	
12:40pm	Open dialogue	Chair: Ferne Edwards, RMIT
1:25pm	Closing remarks	Marta Fernandez, RMIT Europe
1:30pm	Networking lunch	
2:30pm	Event closes	

Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
AECOM	Director Buildings and Places Barcelona	Eric	Trillo
AMS Institute	MSc MADE researcher	Noelle	Teh
Arup	Associate Director	Susana	Saiz
BCD Barcelona Centre for Design	Food Project Manager	Anna	Cancer
Barcelona Wildlife Tours	Biologist and tourist guide	Monica	Navarro
Bax & Company	Innovation Consultant for Sustainable Cities	Sofia	Aivalioti
Bax & Company	Partner & Director	Sebastian	van Herk
BCD Barcelona Centre for Design	Project Manager - Circular Economy & Design	Alba	Obiols
Belle Property	Business Development Manager	Sohail	Foryabee
Bruno Remoue & Associates	Architect	Julie	Dalgier
Culinary Institute of Barcelona	Sales Manager	José Alberto	Calderón Calvo

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Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
DAW Office	Project Manager	Karim	Masri
Diputació Barcelona	Head of Unit. Agricultural Spaces Management	Sonia	Callau
Diputació Barcelona	Architect	Montserrat	Obiols Acebron
École Nationale d'Architecture de Tétouan	Professor / Researcher	William	Kutz
ECOMOLL	Biology	Ana	Ruiz
EIPA	Researcher	Julia	Bosse
EMF Landscape Architecture	Director	Martí	Franch
Freelance	Urban Planning Development	Sergi	Gómez Planella
Freelance	Freelance Translator & Writer	Sigrid	Ehrmann
Fundació Espigoladors	Gleaning Coordinator	Marc	Farres
Fundació Sigea	Director	Xavier	Núñez

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Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
Granollers City Council	Rural Development Engineer	Vicenç	Planas
Hábil Hábitat	Associate	María Teresa	Machado R
Huertos in the Sky	Founder	Adela	Martínez
Hume	Student Strategic Planner	Giselle	Osborne
IAAC	Head of Studies	Mathilde	Marengo
IAAC	Student	Eli	Munn
ICLEI	Senior Communications Officer	Thea	Buckle
ICRA	Research Technician	Joana	Castellar
ICRA	Professor	Ignasi	Rodriguez-Roda
ICRA and LEQUIA-UdG	Research Professor	Joaquim	Comas
ICTA / Universitat Autònoma of Barcelona	Postdoctoral Researcher	Filka	Sekulova

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Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
IETCC-CSIC	Researcher	Guadalupe	Gómez Ruiz
Independent	Scientific Project Manager/ Plant Research Science	Erica	Duarte
Is Global	Outreach Technician	Celia	Santos Tapia
ISGlobal	Pre-doctoral Researcher	Asya	Dimitrova
ISGlobal	Postdoctoral Researcher	Monica	Ubalde
ISGlobal	PhD Researcher	Maria	Toda
ISGlobal - Barcelona Institute for Global Health	Outreach Manager	Raul	Toran
KU Leuven	PhD candidate	Jolein	Bergers
Madrid City Council	Technician at Climate Change Department	Luis	Tejero
Madrid City Council	SG Energy and Climate Change	Juan	Azcárate

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Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
MataAlta Studio	CEO, Designer, Engineer	Sergio	Carratala Lamarca
NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Associate Professor	Ida Nilstad	Pettersen
OUA group	Architect Urban Planer	Núria	Noguer Pujadas
PROMERCA	GM Adviser	Ramon	Hereter
Richard Sekinger - studio für kunst und architektur	Architect	Friedrich	Bader
Sawcer	Founder	Adrienne	Fanning
Sempergreen	Sales Manager	Antoni	Amich
Sustainable Tapas Project	Founder	Fatima	Delgado
Terrassa City Council	Councillor Urban Planning and Sustainability	Carles	Caballero Peña
Terrassa City Council	Directora Urban Planning and Sustainability	Escudé Blasi	Cristina
TBi	Founding Partner	Xavier	Costa
UBC	Associate Professor	Jordi	Honey-Roses

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Seminar registrants*

Organisation	Role	Name	Surname
University of Barcelona	Social Anthropology	Anibal	Arregui
University of Cambridge	PhD Candidate and Research Associate	Mathilda	Rosengren
University of Wollongong, Australia	Senior Lecturer	Leah	Gibbs
University of Lleida	Associate Professor	Pilar	Mallol Casals
University of Lleida	Assistant Professor	Gabriel	Pérez
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Professor	Leandro	Navarro
Verdeo biotech	Journalist	Goizeder	Azúa
W2 Studio	Architecture and Energy Efficiency Strategist	Nuria Isabel	Widmann
Worldline	Global Head of Blockchain Solutions	Manuel	Machado
XDI	Consultant	Sascha	Suessspeck
ZER Moinès Llevant	Academic	Joaquín	Jiménez Godoy

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Event partners

This event is affiliated with the EdiCitNet project. The EdiCitNet project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 776665

